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Impact from 25 years of collaboration with Myanmar

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At 211 kg capita⁻¹ y⁻¹, Myanmar has the highest consumption of milled rice in the world. Not unexpectedly, with this level of consumption, rice production is the predominant activity in the national economy, contributing around one-third of the nation's gross domestic product. Hence, increasing rice production is vital to the general development of the economy as well as to food security in the country.

IRRI has collaborated with the Government of Myanmar over the past 25 years to help the country increase rice productivity. There have been five major bilateral collaborations based in Myanmar and numerous projects based at IRRI headquarters in Los Baños (Shrestha et al 2002). This paper reports on an ex post economic impact evaluation of the IRRI-Myanmar collaborative activities, funded mainly by two Canadian agencies, the Canadian International Development Agency (CIDA) and the International Development Research Centre (IDRC).

Rice area, yield, and production in Myanmar have all increased during the last 4 decades (see figure). From 1975 to 2000, rice production increased from 9.3 million t to 20 million t, an increase of 115% (FAO 2002). This increase is equivalent to a compound growth rate of more than 2.5% y⁻¹ (see table). The increase in production is attributed to a rise in both yield and cropping intensity. From 1976 to 1985, Myanmar achieved a high growth rate in production of 5.6% y⁻¹ despite a slight decline in rice area. During 1986-2000, the growing of a second rice crop in the summer season was the main source of growth in production.

Rice production growth patterns, 1961–2000. Source: Shrestha et al (2002).

Average annual compound growth rate, 1961-2000 (% y⁻¹).

Item	1961-75	1976-85	1986-95	1996-99	1976-2000
Production (t ratio)	1.13 (2.62)	5.62 (6.27)	3.36 (4.03)	3.78 (1.12)	2.49 (9.25)
Area (t ratio)	0.41 (1.70)	-0.69 (-1.93)	3.13 (5.42)	0.26 (0.13)	0.97 (4.99)
Yield (t ratio)	0.72 (2.89)	6.31 (7.13)	0.23 (0.69)	3.50 (2.43)	1.52 (5.00)

Source: FAO database 2002. Note: Growth rates estimated by fitting semilogarithmic trend lines to time-series data. Numbers within parentheses are t ratio of estimated growth rates.

The adoption of modern rice varieties (MVs) as well as higher cropping intensity are the main sources of increased yield. These varieties have been adopted on almost 60% of the total rice area of 6 million ha. Almost all of the irrigated rice area and up to 79% of the rainfed area of the southern deltaic regions are planted to MVs. The MVs developed by IRRI are sown on more than 50% of the total area planted to MVs. The popular IRRI MVs are IR5 and its derivatives. The yield advantage of these MVs over traditional ones is estimated to be in the range of 25–50%. The increase in rice production that can be attributed to MVs is estimated to be from 1.6 million t to 3.2 million t y⁻¹. This represents an increase in the gross value of \$160 million to \$320 million y⁻¹ when valued at \$100 t⁻¹. The corresponding financial gain to farmers is around \$22 million y⁻¹ when valued at a market exchange rate of US\$1 = K 340. The benefit-cost analysis shows that the economic rate of return to the improved

rice technology in Myanmar is 155% y⁻¹ over the past 25 years. For the total investment of more than \$2.2 million in the program, there has been a net gain of \$140 million during the period.

In addition to these quantifiable direct economic benefits, other long-term benefits were also realized from the crop management and farming systems research and from capacity building. Some of these benefits are

- Farming systems research on nutrient management developed extensive strategies for a balanced nutrient supply at lower cost. The studies showed that improved nutrient management practices perform as well as applying recommended levels of expensive inorganic fertilizers.
- Cropping systems and crop-livestock research activities showed that multicropping of rice with other crops improved farmers' livelihood and also helped achieve the national goal of increasing the production of edible oil, pulse, and industrial crops.
- Cropping systems research aimed at identifying optimum cropping patterns in the rice-based systems showed excellent potential for intensifying land use by dry seeding rice as opposed to the traditional practice of transplanting. This practice contributed to the expansion of a second crop in areas previously left fallow following the first rice crop.
- More than 270 researchers from key NARES received training on various aspects of rice production, research planning, and management. The training received at IRRI is viewed as vital and integral to keeping Myanmar's service personnel attuned to the changing trends of science and technology.

References

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 Shrestha S, Bell MA, Marcotte PL. 2002. An economic impact assessment of Myanmar-IRRI country programs. In: IRRI country report. International Rice Research Institute, Los Baños, Philippines. (in press)